

THE CURRENT STATE OF DEVELOPING SPEECH CULTURE IN FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON AN AXIOLOGICAL APPROACH

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Abstract. *The study of adherence to the norms of the Uzbek literary language by university students, the general and distinctive features of the communicative qualities that ensure the cultural level of speech, simple and appropriate speech according to the rules of speech etiquette, concise and meaningful speech, maintaining speech etiquette in the presence of parents, elders, and mentors, as well as the development of the ability to express thoughts clearly, correctly, and fluently, using logical arguments in conversation. Mastery of speech culture implies the effective use of the capabilities of language levels and its various expressive means, enabling the creation of rich and meaningful speech. The retention of speech in consciousness, its synthesis, as well as the ability to repeatedly edit the expressed thoughts in speech activities and the use of proverbs, sayings, wise words and phraseological units contribute to the enhancement of students' speech activity.*

Keywords: *axiological approach, speech culture, reading culture, speech etiquette, ethics of speech, ethical level of speech culture, logical, creative, scientific thinking, basics of speech culture, speech appropriateness.*

According to the linguist V.Z.Demyankov “Based on the chosen communicative strategy, a single piece of information can be expressed differently in various contexts. There can also be a significant gap between the organized information stored in a person’s memory and its verbal form. The modules involved in text creation include the information generator and the articulators. Speech, particularly the creation of text, follows not only semantic and grammatical rules but also specific norms for presenting information. The schemes used to describe events vary, and texts emerge in accordance with the interconnection of these events”.

In communication, information is exchanged, and regardless of its form, data accumulates within it. As a result, conditions are created for the development of speech culture.

Essentially, expressive reading is the ability to read a specific literary work or an excerpt from it in a way that conveys the author’s emotions. Expressive reading is considered a natural outcome and an objective indicator of conscious reading, as it ensures both intellectual and emotional comprehension of the work. It enhances the educational impact of the piece, positively influences the formation of students’ speech culture, and helps achieve expressiveness in speech.

Speech culture is closely connected to book reading and its critical and analytical synthesis. Therefore, in this process, future teachers study the rules and principles of constructing culturally appropriate speech in educational activities, expressive reading of texts and the art and culture of reading.

In the development of speech culture, functional styles play an important role: conversational, scientific, official, journalistic, and artistic styles. It is also essential to have knowledge about writing and formalizing official documents in the state language. “Since stylistics

also studies speech styles, it is in this very context that its relationship with speech culture emerges. The theory of speech culture, by its nature, requires a detailed reflection on language styles and the unique features and possibilities of each style. The communicative qualities of speech usually vary depending on the style: one may be better expressed in a certain style, while another may be less effectively conveyed in a different one... Stylistics and speech culture do not contradict each other—instead, they complement each other. Although they are separate fields, they serve one another. Speech styles and speech culture together form a set of mutually reinforcing and necessary skills in a person’s activity. This is because a speaker who uses speech styles appropriately and effectively in communication becomes a participant in speech culture who also possesses speech etiquette”.

- Developing the speaker as a subject of cultured speech;
- Transforming specific information into verbal expression;
- Learning the language and using its levels effectively;
- Fostering new perspectives and creative thinking;
- Improving adherence to speech etiquette in group and communicative situations;
- Developing skills for observing speech decorum and speech ethics, as well as drawing logical conclusions and reaching sound decisions.

Furthermore, speech etiquette plays an invaluable role in the development of speech culture. Speech is a cornerstone that reflects a person’s level of upbringing, intellect, inner world, spirituality, reasoning, and knowledge. A person who has mastered speech etiquette can deliver necessary messages and information to the listener with respect. Even unpleasant news can be conveyed in such a way that the listener experiences no undue distress or emotional turmoil. To achieve this, every cultured person—including medical professionals—must know linguistic norms, including pronunciation, stress, word usage, and sentence structure; be able to use expressive means of language appropriately for the communicative context; read expressively; comprehend what they read; and clearly express their thoughts both orally and in writing.

Additionally, teaching information and texts is praiseworthy for its importance in the development of speech culture.

Speech culture is a social phenomenon that forms part of the overall human culture. It is based on adherence to high moral standards during communication, using impactful, beautiful, and appropriate language; practicing the culture of listening, conversation, and debate; and treating language with attention and care in speech. As poets say, using every word “as if choosing a beloved” forms the foundation of speech culture. Stylistics and speech culture are not the same, but they are interrelated phenomena that complement and elevate one another.

In our view, highly developed axiological competence and a sense of respect for national values reflect the idea that choosing the right words in a speech situation is akin to selecting a beloved—an act of deliberate care.

Speech culture teaches the Eastern codes of politeness and communication, from simple greetings to how, when, where and to whom one should speak. These aspects are instilled in students during the study of phonetic phenomena and language rules.

Today, the concept of speech culture also includes speech etiquette. It refers to expressing thoughts independently, fluently, beautifully, and appropriately to the speech context. A refined speech culture is a key indicator of a society’s cultural and educational progress and a reflection

of the nation's spiritual development. The effectiveness of verbal communication depends on speech culture, for only cultured speech possesses true communicative power.

To ensure the correctness feature in the written form of the literary language, two additional types of norms must be followed. These norms are as follows:

1) Spelling (orthographic) norms

2) Punctuation norms:

Topics:

- Introduction
- Speech, its forms, types, and styles
- Speech culture, rhetoric, and oratory
- Oratory and speech culture in antiquity. History of Eastern oratory. Oratory and speech culture in Central Asia
- Norms and rules of cultured speech
- Communicative qualities of cultured speech
- Speech culture and the expressive means of language
- Recommendations for organizing practical lessons
- Speech culture. Oratory. Colloquium on speech forms and types
- Exercises on pronunciation and spelling norms of cultured speech
- Exercises on grammatical and stylistic norms of cultured speech
- Communicative qualities of written cultured speech
- Communicative qualities of oral cultured speech
- Training on brevity in speech.

These kinds of topics were taught to future students in the 11th grade of general education schools. It can be said that speech culture has been consistently taught within the language education system.

In the textbook “Teacher’s Speech Culture” authored by N.Mahmudov “The theoretical foundations and practical issues of speech culture are covered, with a specific focus on the teacher’s verbal activity. The relationship of speech culture with other subjects is presented. The main communicative qualities of speech—correctness, clarity, logic, purity, richness, conciseness and expressiveness—are thoroughly defined, and practical recommendations are summarized based on the analysis of numerous factual examples. Attention is also paid to deficiencies that may arise due to improper speech technique, and practical advice is provided for eliminating them”.

Syllabus, goals, and objectives of the course “Teacher’s Speech Culture”:

- Speech culture and its relationship with other disciplines
- Main communicative qualities of cultured speech
- Correctness of speech
- Clarity of speech
- Logic of speech
- Purity of speech
- Richness of speech
- Conciseness of speech
- Expressiveness of speech
- Teacher’s speech technique.

This subject, taught across all disciplines in the higher education system, helps students develop the skills to speak properly and observe speech etiquette in both educational processes and family life.

Language ability is developed and enhanced throughout a person's entire life.

The term ability is often understood as "a psychological trait that distinguishes one person from another and determines the degree of success in a particular activity, in connection with that person's knowledge, skills and competencies.

A responsible approach to speech culture in one's professional activity fosters the development of complex synthetic traits. Additionally, in interpersonal communication, the relationship between speaker and listener is expressed. In such situations, engaging in communication based on mutual understanding and adherence to speech culture reveals their interests, life experience and expressed viewpoints. In this process, it is crucial to direct students toward research, motivation, and the development of cognitive skills to be used in their speech. Working with texts is one of the most essential tasks in the development of speech culture.

Text reading and working with texts include several stages which are important for teaching reading, especially since the texts students encounter in higher grades are longer and structurally more complex, both in content and format.

In some literature, working with texts is divided into four stages:

1. Preparation stage
2. Direct reading stage
3. Post-reading stage
4. Creative stage

In the first stage, new and unfamiliar lexical and grammatical material in the text is introduced and explained. Therefore, this stage is divided into two parts:

- 1) Lexical section
- 2) Grammatical section

Even if the text contains no unfamiliar words or grammar, these sections are not omitted—they are used to refresh previously learned material.

In the second stage, the text is directly read by students, and they are taught to understand what they read. Both silent and oral reading are practiced in this stage.

In the third stage, comprehension is checked through various exercises. Tasks may include rephrasing or expanding the content. Students add their own knowledge and build upon the content.

In the fourth, creative stage students express their own independent opinions and reflections on the content of the text.

Moreover, working with such texts helps future teachers develop their speech culture in terms of logical content.

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